

Spectral Leakage in Matrix Inversion Tomosynthesis

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Abstract— Matrix Inversion Tomosynthesis (MITS) is a linear MIMO system, which deblurs Shift And Add (SAA) reconstructed tomosynthesis slices by applying deconvolution in spectral domain. When implementing MITS, some difficulties, important from both theoretical and practical viewpoints should be considered. In this paper new combined methods are proposed to tackle one of them, the truncation artifact caused by spectral leakage in thoracic imaging using DTS. The effect of the proposed methods is illustrated by coronal human chest slices, validated and compared quantitatively.

Keywords—MITS; tomosynthesis; deconvolution; spectral leakage; truncation artifact; MIMO system; inverse problem

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital tomosynthesis is a relatively new imaging modality that computes reconstructed slice images from a set of low-dose X-ray projections acquired over a limited angle range [1]. The basic arrangement of a linear chest tomosynthesis is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic arrangement of linear chest tomosynthesis

In a linear tomosynthesis arrangement the X-ray beam-source and a flat panel detector move continuously in parallel along the y axis in opposite directions. During this motion, at about 40-60 different positions, projection images are acquired. According to Fig. 1. these images are obtained in the x-y plane, where x axis denotes the row-, and y axis the column directions. From these projections coronal slice images of the 3D examined volume (e.g. the lung) are reconstructed (one of them is marked by the dashed line in the figure) using reconstruction algorithms. Most of these algorithms are modifications of the algorithms used in CT image reconstruction (e.g. BP, FBP, ART, ML-EM, [2]), with the exception of the matrix inversion tomosynthesis (MITS) [3], an algorithm developed directly for tomosynthesis, which deblurs the reconstructed slices calculated by the Shift and Add (SAA) algorithm [3], [4].

The input projection images that are acquired by the detector can be modelled as the sum of the shifted projections of the coronal slices of the examined volume:

$$I_j^{(l)} = \sum_k R_j^{(k)} * H^{(l,k)} \quad (1)$$

Here $I_j^{(l)}$ denotes the j -th column of the l -th input projection image, $R_j^{(k)}$ denotes the j -th column of the central projection of the k -th reconstructed coronal slice, $*$ denotes the convolution and, $H^{(l,k)}$ denotes the weight function between the k -th coronal slice and the l -th input projection image. The goal of the reconstruction method is to estimate the R functions from the input projections. $H^{(k,1)}$ is a shifted Dirac-delta function that can be derived from the acquisition geometry [4]. (1) can be also examined in Fourier domain:

$$\hat{\mathbf{i}}_j(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{H}}(\omega) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_j(\omega) \quad (2)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{i}}_j(\omega)$ denotes the column vector containing the spectral components of the j -th columns of the input projections, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j(\omega)$ gives a column vector constructed similarly from the j -th columns of the slices of the examined volume:

$$\hat{\mathbf{i}}_j(\omega) = \left[FT_\omega \{I_j^{(1)}\} \quad FT_\omega \{I_j^{(2)}\} \quad \dots \quad FT_\omega \{I_j^{(N_p)}\} \right]^T \quad (3)$$

$FT_\omega \{ \cdot \}$ is the operator of 1D continuous Fourier transform at ω frequency, and N_p denotes the number of input projection images. The matrix that is denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{H}}(\omega)$ is defined by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}(\omega)_{(l,k)} = FT_\omega \{ H^{(l,k)} \} \quad (4)$$

Although SAA is simple and easy to implement, its results, the reconstructed slice images are rather poor. The SAA reconstructed slices can be represented as convolution of the actual in-plane structures and a blurring function relating how structures located in one plane are reconstructed in another. So it can be modelled by a MIMO shift invariant linear system:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_j(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{G}}(\omega) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}}_j(\omega) \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{G}}(\omega)$ denotes the matrix of the SAA reconstruction, $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_j(\omega)$ gives a column vector containing the spectral com-

ponents of the j -th columns of the SAA reconstructed slices similarly to (3). The exact value of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}(\omega)$ is defined by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}}(\omega)_{(l,k)} = \overline{\hat{\mathbf{H}}(\omega)_{(k,l)}} \quad (6)$$

where \bar{a} stands for the operator of complex conjugating. SAA slices can also be modelled as the sum of the shifted projections of the examined volume's ideally thin slices:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_j(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{F}}(\omega) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}}_j(\omega) \quad (7)$$

while $\hat{\mathbf{F}}(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{H}}(\omega)^* \cdot \hat{\mathbf{H}}(\omega)$ denotes the blurring matrix at ω . Based on this equation, the MITS estimates the slice images by a deconvolution which is implemented in Fourier domain:

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_j(\omega) = \hat{\mathbf{F}}(\omega)^{-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{s}}_j(\omega) \quad (8)$$

Contrary to the classical image deconvolution problems, in this case a MIMO system is inverted, which requires consistency of the input projections.

The whole algorithm has three significant difficulties: (*) using discrete Fourier transform (DFT) for (2)-(8), spectral leakage may happen; (**) $\mathbf{F}(\omega)$ is ill-conditioned (mainly at low frequencies) as it is shown in [5], and (***) the examined 3D volume can't be modelled by finite number, ideally thin, zero-thick slices [4].

This paper focuses on the first problem. A composite method is proposed which can effectively handle the spectral leakage problem of the MITS reconstruction (here and hereafter in MITS we mean the cascade of SAA reconstruction (5) and the deblurring step (8)). In the next section the artifacts caused by spectral leakage and the proposed method to reduce these are described. The validation of the proposed method and a comparison to [5] is presented in the last section.

II. ARTIFACTS CAUSED BY SPECTRAL LEAKAGE

Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) implicitly assumes that the sampled, finite length signal is only a period of a periodic signal. The side effect of the DFT calculated spectrum caused by the violation of this assumption is the so-called spectral leakage. In MITS reconstruction this causes y -directional intensity oscillation pattern over the whole image (called boundary artifact). In Fig. 3. a human thoracic coronal plane is shown (one of the corresponding input projections is in Fig. 2.), which is reconstructed by MITS without handling the spectral leakage problem. In the figure the area circumscribed by an ellipsoid shows low frequency artifacts, while the arrow points to an area where high frequency artifacts (horizontal lines) are generated, both are due to spectral leakage. The effect of spectral leakage can be reduced if the image is modified in such a way that there is a smooth continuation between the lower and the upper parts of the images (the image can be considered as one period of a periodic signal without any abrupt change at the borders of a period). Additionally due to the periodic assumption of the DFT in (8), the SAA reconstructed slices have to be extrapolated periodically in vertical direction (along y axis). Otherwise, due

to the so called wrap-around effect, the reconstruction of anatomical structures located near to the top of a slice depends on lower placed regions of the SAA slices (e.g. the reconstruction of the apex of the lung depends on the SAA reconstruction of the diaphragm). The minimal height of the extrapolated area can be determined analytically from the inverse Fourier transform of the blurring matrix ($\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ in (7)).

Based on our previous publications ([6] and [4]), in the case of MITS it is reasonable to reconstruct significantly more (N_R) slices than the number of input projections (N_P), but this means that the deblurring equation (7) is overdetermined. This implies that more SAA slices are reconstructed than the number of input projections. If we extrapolate the SAA slices one by one, than probably there will not exist N_P realistic projection images that satisfy equation (5).

As our proposed extrapolating method can only extrapolate the slice or the projection images one by one (an alternative method that takes into account all of the projections/ SAA slices is under investigation) the input projection images are extrapolated. In this case (5) in discrete Fourier domain produces adequately extrapolated SAA slices.

Fig. 2. Example of an input projection image.

Fig. 3. MITS reconstructed thoracic plane without compensation of the spectral leakage artifact.

A. Windowing and Post filtering

In digital signal processing, the spectral leakage effect is usually reduced by windowing the signal before calculating its spectrum. However, windowing as an amplitude reduction effect is significant in the top and the bottom of the reconstructed slices if the input projections are windowed. This effect can't be effectively handled after the deconvolution step (8), as if we apply windowing, the whole reconstruction becomes a shift variant linear system. To compensate this phenomenon, the reconstructed slices are post-filtered by dividing the reconstructed slice images with the intensities of the reconstructed slices calculated from the above input simulated projection images:

$$W^{(i)}(j, k) = w(j) \quad (9)$$

where $w(\cdot)$ is the windowing function, and $W^{(i)}$ is the i -th generated windowing input image. In order to avoid dividing by a small number in the post-filtering step Hamming window function (with $\alpha = 0.54$) was chosen. It is important to note that post-filtering based compensation is only a heuristic step, it can not compensate perfectly the artifact caused by windowing. The effect of the whole compensation is illustrated in Fig. 4. due to the numerical instability caused by the post-filtering step, the uppermost and the lowermost rows of the reconstructed slices are usually noisy (marked by the ellipsoids in Fig. 4.). This effect can significantly weak the diagnostic value of the reconstruction, therefore some further steps are required to reduce this artifact.

Fig. 4. Result of the windowing and post filtering compensation for the same slice as illustrated by Fig. 3.

B. Smooth extrapolation

The basics of this method are described in [7]. The main idea is based on that the vertical intensity oscillation pattern (which is an effect of the spectral leakage) on the reconstructed slices is caused by the discontinuities between the first and the last rows of the input projections. These discontinuities can be minimized by applying a maximally smooth interpolation between the upper and lower ends of the projection images:

$$\mathbf{E}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\Gamma}^{(i)} \\ \mathbf{\Gamma}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Here $\mathbf{E}^{(i)}$ denotes the i -th extrapolated projection, $\mathbf{\Gamma}^{(i)}$ denotes the i -th input projection, $\mathbf{\Gamma}^{(i)}$ denotes the image part calculated by the extrapolation in the case of the i -th projection. $\mathbf{\Gamma}^{(i)}$ is calculated in order to get a maximally smooth extrapolated image ($\mathbf{E}^{(i)}$), where the metric of smoothness is defined by:

$$\|\Delta\{\mathbf{E}^{(i)}\}\|_F^2 \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta\{\cdot\}$ denotes the discrete, two-dimensional, vertically circular Laplacian of Gaussian operator, and $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm. The problem can be formalized as a quadratic programming (QP) problem, which can be effectively solved in this special case.

C. Mixture of the two algorithms

According to the validation of the whole process (it is described in details in the next section) the spectral distortion caused by the extrapolation is larger than the spectral distortion caused by windowing the projections, however the intensity reduction at the upper and lower bounds of the images does not occur. Therefore we blend the two reconstructions calculated from the two sets of preprocessed projections (one of them is modified by the windowing and post-filtering method, while the other is modified by smooth extrapolation) with spatial varying weights. Near the boundary of the reconstructed slices the reconstruction calculated after the smooth extrapolation dominates while the windowing based solution dominates in the central parts. The result of this blending is illustrated by Fig. 5. The difference between the results of the mixing and the smooth extrapolation based methods is moderated in real slice images. Based on the numerical validation the mixing based correction outperforms the smooth extrapolation based method.

III. VALIDATION AND CONCLUSIONS

The noise sensitivity of the MITS reconstruction depends on the spatial frequency of the input projections [4]. Therefore such a validation is used that examines the spectrum of the distortion of the reconstructed slices. As the applied extrapolation can't be modelled by shift invariant linear approach, the distortion can't be examined by analytic methods (e.g. measuring the MTF). However, to estimate the distortion is possible by comparing the original slices and the MITS calculated slices reconstructed from the projections of the same artificial volume.

In contrast to the CT, the DTS projections are obtained only from a limited angle range. This implies that the thickness of the reconstructed slices is bigger and depends on the spatial frequency of the images [5]. In the low frequency domain the reconstructed slices are significantly larger than in the higher frequency domain. This means that the low frequency components of the reconstruction depend on a thicker part of the examined volume (e.g. the DC component depends on the whole volume). In order to separate this effect from the

Fig. 5. Result of mixed reconstruction.

degradation caused by the spectral leakage, reconstructions are calculated from projections of artificial volumes containing only a few (in our case 4), ideally thin nonempty coronal slices of a chest reconstruction, placed as far from each other as possible (there was approx. 60 mm-s between adjacent slices). 15 such volumes were used. Formally, in the validation the error of reconstruction of the nonempty slices was computed as:

$$err(\omega) = \left\langle \frac{\left| FT_{\omega} \{ \mathbf{R}_j^{(i,k)} \} - FT_{\omega} \{ \mathbf{P}_j^{(i,k)} \} \right|}{\left| FT_{\omega} \{ \mathbf{P}_j^{(i,k)} \} \right|} \right\rangle \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_j^{(i,k)}$ denotes the j -th column of the k -th nonempty slice of the i -th reconstruction, $\mathbf{P}_j^{(i,k)}$ denotes the j -th column of the corresponding projected slices, $\langle \rangle$ denotes averaging over i, j, k . $\lambda_{(i,k)}$ denotes the un-normalized MTF between the in-plane signal positioned at the i -th volume's k -th nonempty slice and its reconstruction. The ideal MTF of the MITS reconstruction can be calculated as it is described in [8]. In order to minimize the DFT caused spectral distortion windowing is applied before calculating the Fourier transform. It is important to note that this windowing makes this kind of validation biased towards to the windowing based extrapolation method since it underweights the border parts of the slices, where the windowing based extrapolation method mainly creates artifacts.

In the validation of the reduction of the spectral leakage 4 different methods were compared: (1) windowing and post filtering, (2) smooth extrapolation, (3) mixture of these two techniques, and (4) a method described in [3] ("base method"). The error curves are plotted in Fig. 6. Based on the result, we can see that both the windowing and post filtering and the smooth extrapolation methods outperform the base method. From the two methods the error of the windowing based extrapolation is less in wide part of frequency domain but in image domain the intensity artifact described before degrades the diagnostic value of the reconstructions. It is also concluded that the error of applying the mixture correction

Fig. 6. Result of the validation. All of the three methodes introduced by this paper outperform the base method.

method is not significantly larger than the error of the windowing based method under the bandwidth of the projected slices (1.1 cycles/mm). This bandwidth is approximately the average bandwidth of the chest tomosynthesis slice images.

Based on our experiments and the results of the validation, the mixture of the two compensation methods effectively reduces the artifacts caused by the spectral leakage without degrading the slices at their borders. Also we believe that extrapolation methods can significantly be improved by taking into account all of the projections during extrapolation (now projections are extrapolated one by one). These methods can handle cases, when there exists part of the volume which is projected into only a subset of the projections (illustrated by the shaded area of Fig. 1.), so they better fit to the whole MIMO system of the reconstruction. Such a method is under investigation.

IV. REFERENCES

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